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Innovative Service Technologies in the Hotel Business

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***Abstract.** As is known, innovation in the hotel business is an improvement in the current state and degree of renewal of the hotel enterprise. Therefore, innovations must be new, meet market demand, benefit the manufacturer and contribute to quality customer service.*

***Keywords:** tourism, service, hotel, tour operator, guests.*

INTRODUCTION

The variety of modern hotel rooms allows you to stay in very comfortable hotels, inns, motels, boarding houses, etc. for relatively little money. Quality service is the key to success in any hotel business. No matter how many stars a hotel has, guests can stay and fall in love with the service. Tourists know how boring things ruin a hotel stay: sometimes you have to call the hotel staff for various service reasons: phone repair, quick cleaning, errors in media reports. All these mistakes can quickly become a thing of the past because high-tech hotels are just around the corner.

Based on statistical data, potential hotel customers are increasingly staying for a long period. This begs the question: why does this happen? This is not only convenient, but also safe, because a person, having paid the amount for accommodation, is released from all responsibility for the maintenance of his home. A hotel is a place where the guest is always greeted with a smile, always ready to help and satisfy all needs, with care and good nature.

Innovative service technologies are used in all areas of the hotel and on its territory. The significant difference between a hotel and a hotel is mainly related to the quality of service. The latest data communications devices are often installed in hotel industry centers and conference rooms. The operation of the hotel is very specific: the restaurant, lobby and rooms have various integrated power sources, light and temperature provide a comfortable environment for guests. This system allows you to increase the authority and status of the hotel and its owner. The Ambassador comes up with unique innovations to show his confession. For example, the well-developed Dostar hotel, in forming a corporate identity, attracted attention to fashion trends in the field of hotel innovation and aroma marketing. Nano-aromatization, which is one of the latest developments in the field, is widely used in this hotel. Its operating technique is simple: built-in ventilation with a unique system that turns aromatic oils into microparticles, which in turn fill all rooms with aroma. With this innovation, a light citrus

aroma is felt in the hotel lobby and rooms, and the aroma of vanilla and coffee is felt in the restaurant. Of course, the latest technologies are used to ensure the safety of hotel guests and staff. All rooms and office doors are equipped with Vingcard electronic locks, which can be opened using a key card. You can take detailed readings from any lock at any time. Swiss hotels are known for their high level of service and special attention to the privacy and security of their stay. For example, the Grand Hotel Le Richemond, located in Geneva, and a list of other hotels offer their guests personal bodyguards. This trend is consolidated not only in Europe, but also in the most remote corners of the world. Including bodyguards, Cordova Reef Village Resort 4*, which is a resort hotel on the southern island of Mactan (Philippines), now provides bodyguards.

A priority for each hotel room is to introduce such technical innovations as installing a single panel of connectors for a variety of audio and video devices. This is convenient to use and will allow the guest to connect their equipment. Interactive television system is one of the most popular innovations and is used by many hotels today. Installing this system is an expensive process, but it is worth the price. Most often, this system represents information and video content: films, music, satellite television. Such a service in the room will definitely be a pleasant bonus for the guest. To obtain an additional source of income, paid functions can be added to the main services of this innovation. It is believed that technology in the hotel business is aimed at improving the comfort of guests exclusively, but this is not so. Innovations also help service staff: specialized equipment can simplify the cleaning process, it can also create an optimal microclimate and significantly reduce labor costs for maintaining rooms in order. In the near future, these systems will be further developed through the dissemination and modernization of service systems and technologies. There are systems that can be obtained by subscription (SAAS technology). There is great demand among seasonal hotels (ski and resort). With the help of these technologies, the owner does not have to spend large sums of money on purchasing expensive software, as well as pay a small amount of operating costs for the implementation of the subscription. Therefore, using this system you can get to any hotel, including mini-hotels. In order for hotels to feel competitive, it is necessary to look for new ways to increase the attractiveness and accessibility of the services provided. Following the advent of technologies for the dissemination of innovative electronic booking systems, allowing all booking processes to be carried out online through all television sales and integration with hotel management systems. One of the most important objectives of a hotel is access to a wide range of sales channels. Through what channels and how to make sales is a matter of promotion policy, which depends on the workload at the hotel, the current season and other factors.

Today, everyone is trying to compete and demonstrate their advantages, which certainly leads to the creation of several high-tech innovations necessary to demonstrate leadership in the market. They make life more varied, interesting and easier, maximize time and effort, and bring additional income. Innovative solutions play an important role in business development and occupy a special place in the hospitality industry. Today, most hotels are automated because the benefits of using these systems are obvious not only to people in the hospitality industry, but also to customers. There are many ways for hotel guests to benefit, not just discounts and special offers. Innovative solutions are decisive factors in the choice of modern guests.

The analysis of existing hotel technologies revealed the presence of technological gaps (technological and automated technological orientation), the need for technological changes in the direction of comprehensive automation and the need to introduce technological innovations by developing a technological standard for various accommodation facilities. Technology transfer is determined by the presence of physical, legal and human components. The greatest influence on the implementation of technology is exerted by the human factor - the psychology of perception and the level of qualifications of personnel. The legal component determines the creation of social and technological standards for the introduction of modern hotel technologies. The material component is determined by the technical equipment, type and comfort of housing.

By analyzing the high-tech innovations of hotel automation, a specific base can be identified, becoming the last word of the team and promoting competition. Interactive TV Systems - today there is a huge variety of models for any, even the most unpretentious taste, for example, the Hoist Technology company offers several types of interactive systems: - easy TV is specially designed for cheap hotels that cannot afford to completely replace the television park on the hotel TV system, since this system does not require a classic interactive system with a standard set of interactive functions. In most cases, the system includes content that can only please the guest: movies, satellite channels and music. In addition to content, the systems include services that not only help the customer stay updated on hotel deals, but also the hotel staff to know the customer's preferences, such as what movie the customer has ordered, what food and drinks you prefer, you can order them through room service. Now Wi-Fi should be in every hotel room. For many guests, and especially for business people, wireless Internet with the ability to connect to a laptop is now a full-fledged hotel service. The biggest challenge is always providing customers with high-quality, fast and reliable Internet access that they use at home. As a result, hotel wireless Internet access system providers provide hotels with the ability to control settings to ensure access-connection speed, traffic volume and/or prepaid time, etc. The hotel can reduce energy consumption by approximately 30% thanks to an energy management system. A central computer controls and changes the temperature in each hotel room.

By controlling the climate in the device, if reduce costs and help change the environment for the better. A modern hotel is very specific in its operation: lobby, bar, restaurant, unique fitness rooms and trade conferences, all rooms must have different meals. Having a system that can automatically control light emission, change room temperature or activate air conditioning is an undeniable advantage for a hotel owner. An RFID door lock that allows guests to enter their room and other hotel rooms without a key. This innovative mechanism is becoming increasingly popular in hotels around the world because it does not require a key to open. To access the room, the client can use a mobile phone of any brand and not waste time searching for a lost key. Robotics has not bypassed the hotel industry and is already beginning to introduce its innovations into the daily lives of guests, accustoming them to the future.

Thus, I would like to note that innovative processes are an integral part of modern business. Their implementation thanks to the development and improvement of hotels is possible in constantly changing conditions.

Competition in the hotel business is growing steadily, so even the most impeccable reputation and high-quality service are not a guarantee of success. Today you should notice something, show your

individuality. In today's market, new, unusual and original ideas, as well as unique innovative solutions, are welcomed.

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